

1. Guten Appetit!- Polite form of starting a joint meal; Formula for desire at the sight of food.
2. Verschiebe nicht auf morgen, was du heute kannst besorgen- Don't put off until tomorrow what you can do today.
3. an jmdm einen Narren gefressen haben- To love someone very much or to be carried away by someone.
4. hin and her- Back and forth; constant change of direction.
5. sich die Zähne putzen- Brush your teeth.
6. das Rote Kreuz- Red Cross.

Phraseologisms are a special linguistic object that has a number of characteristic properties. The main criteria that determine a phraseological unit are:

1. Polylexicality: Phraseologisms consist of more than one word.
2. Hardness: They are used in the language community in a similar way to a single word.

REFERENCES

1. Moon, R. (1998). *Fixed Expressions and Idioms in English: A Corpus-Based Approach*. Oxford University Press.
2. Fernando, C. (1996). *Idioms and Idiomaticity*. Oxford University Press.
3. Simpson, R. (2000). *Semantic Prosody: A Critical Evaluation*. Routledge.
4. Glucksberg, S. (1993). *Idiom Meanings and Allusional Content*. In C. Cacciari & P. Tabossi (Eds.), *Idioms: Processing, Structure, and Interpretation*, (pp. 3-26). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
5. Nippold, M. A., & Taylor, C. L. (2002). *Judgments of idiom familiarity and transparency: A comparison of children and adolescents*. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 45(2), 384-391.

BORROWING BRILLIANCE: CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING FOREIGN LANGUAGE INNOVATIONS

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Annotation: while foreign experience and innovative technologies hold immense potential for improving foreign language learning, navigating the challenges is critical. By carefully considering cultural context, ensuring equitable access, and investing in teacher training, educators can turn borrowed brilliance into effective learning experiences for all students

Key words: Improve foreign language, cultural incongruence, crucial factor, collaboration and exchange, innovative technologies.

Аннотация: Зарубежный опыт и инновационные технологии обладают огромным потенциалом для улучшения изучения иностранных языков, решение этих проблем имеет решающее значение. Тщательно учитывая культурный контекст, обеспечивая равный доступ и инвестируя в подготовку учителей, преподаватели могут превратить заимствованные таланты в эффективный опыт обучения для всех учащихся

Ключевые слова: Совершенствование иностранного языка, культурное несоответствие, решающий фактор, сотрудничество и обмен, инновационные технологии.

Annotatsiya: Xorijiy tajriba va innovatsion texnologiyalar chet tillarini o'rganishni takomillashtirish uchun ulkan salohiyatga ega bo'lsa-da, muammolarni hal qilish juda muhim. Madaniy kontekstni sinchkovlik bilan ko'rib chiqish, teng huquqli foydalanishni ta'minlash va o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirishga sarmoya kiritish orqali o'qituvchilar o'zlari olgan yorqinlikni barcha talabalar uchun samarali o'rganish tajribasiga aylantirishlari mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tilini yaxshilash, madaniy nomuvofiqlik, hal qiluvchi omil, hamkorlik va almashinuv, innovatsion texnologiyalar.

The quest to improve foreign language learning is a global endeavor. Educators constantly seek out new methods and technologies to make language acquisition more effective and engaging. Borrowing successful approaches from other countries and integrating innovative tools are tempting solutions, but challenges lurk beneath the surface.

One major hurdle is cultural incongruence. A method praised in one country might not resonate with students from a different background. Educational philosophies, learning styles, and even humor can vary significantly. What works wonders in a high-tech Korean classroom might fall flat in a resource-limited African school.

The allure of technology can also be a double-edged sword. While virtual reality simulations or language learning apps offer exciting possibilities, access and infrastructure issues can create a barrier. Not all students have reliable internet connections or access to expensive devices. The digital divide can exacerbate existing inequalities, leaving some students behind.

Teacher training is another crucial factor. Implementing new methods requires educators to be comfortable with the approaches and skilled in using them. A one-size-fits-all professional development program might not equip teachers with the necessary tools to adapt foreign practices to their specific contexts.

Measuring progress can also be tricky. New methods often necessitate reevaluating traditional assessment tools. How do we effectively gauge the impact of a virtual exchange program or a gamified learning app on complex communication skills?

Finally, successful implementation often hinges on collaboration and exchange. Learning from colleagues abroad is invaluable, but forging strong international partnerships takes time and effort. Sharing best practices and adapting successful strategies requires a strong network of educators willing to bridge geographical and cultural divides.

In conclusion, while foreign experience and innovative technologies hold immense potential for improving foreign language learning, navigating the challenges is critical. By carefully considering cultural context, ensuring equitable access, and investing in teacher training, educators can turn borrowed brilliance into effective learning experiences for all students.

REFERENCES

1. "Fundamentals of Economics" by N. Gregory Mankiw and James Hertz
2. "Principles of Economics" N. Gregory Mankiw
3. "General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money" by John Maynard Keynes
4. "Modernization of industry and knowledge dissemination" by Paul Romer

ENHANCING STUDENTS' SPEAKING ABILITY BY USING APHORISMS

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Abstract. The article discusses how aphorisms could be implemented in the educational process as a means of developing students' speaking skill. Aphorisms are authentic material with broad educational potential. Aphorisms play an important role in getting the communicative competence of the target language and the cultural knowledge as well. Careful selection of authentic language material, the use of appropriate methods and techniques contribute to the effective development of students' speaking skill.

Keywords: teaching method, speaking skill, teaching speaking, aphorisms, authentic material, communicative competence, cultural values.